

Supplementary information

Frequent violation of the sonority sequencing principle in hundreds of languages: How often and by which sequences?

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1 Languages in the sample

Languages in the sample are listed in Table 1. Rows are ordered alphabetically by macro-area, family, and name. For each language variety we also cite the nearest available glottocode in version 4.2 (Hammarström et al. 2020). (In cases where glottolog does not yet differentiate between multiple varieties that are distinct in our source data, we use the same glottocode twice, e.g. ayab1239 for Ayapathu and Yintyingka. In the case of Epena Saija and Epena Basurudó, we use glottocode basu1242 which corresponds to a tip in glottolog’s Chocoan family tree, rather than the code epen1239 used by CLICS2, since epen1239 corresponds to an internal node in glottolog’s tree.) The information in Table 1 is also available in the file `language_metadata.tsv`.

Table 1: Languages in the sample

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Americas	Arawakan	Achagua	acha1250	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-achagua
Americas	Arawakan	Baniva	bani1254	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-baniva
Americas	Arawakan	Cabiyari	cabi1241	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-cabiyari
Americas	Arawakan	Curripaco	curr1243	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-curripaco
Americas	Arawakan	Giacone	peri1265	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-giacone
Americas	Arawakan	Piapoco	piap1246	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-piapoco
Americas	Arawakan	Resigaro	resi1247	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-resigaro
Americas	Arawakan	Tariano	peri1265	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tariano
Americas	Arawakan	Wayuu	wayu1243	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-wayuu
Americas	Arawakan	Yucuna	yucu1253	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-yucuna
Americas	Barbacoan	Awa	awac1239	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-awa
Americas	Barbacoan	Chapalaachi	chac1249	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-chapalaachi
Americas	Barbacoan	Guambiano	guam1248	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-guambiano
Americas	Barbacoan	Totoro	toto1306	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-totoro
Americas	Barbacoan	Tsafiquipila	colo1256	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tsafiquipila
Americas	Boran	Bora	nucl1660	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-bora
Americas	Boran	Mirana	mira1254	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-mirana
Americas	Boran	Muinane	muin1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-muinane
Americas	Camsá	Kamsa	cams1241	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-kamsa
Americas	Cariban	Carijona	cari1279	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-carijona
Americas	Cariban	Yukpa	yukp1241	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-yukpa
Americas	Chibchan	Bari	bari1297	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-bari
Americas	Chibchan	Chimila	chim1309	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-chimila
Americas	Chibchan	Dimina	mala1522	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-dimina
Americas	Chibchan	Ika	arhu1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-ika
Americas	Chibchan	Kogui	cogu1240	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-kogui
Americas	Chibchan	Tunebocentral	cent2150	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tunebocentral
Americas	Chocoan	Catio	embe1260	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-catio
Americas	Chocoan	Emberachami	embe1262	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberachami
Americas	Chocoan	Emberadarien	nort2972	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberadarien
Americas	Chocoan	Emberatado	embe1261	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberatado
Americas	Chocoan	Epenabasurudo	basu1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-epenasajija
Americas	Chocoan	Epenasajija	basu1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-epenasajija
Americas	Chocoan	Wounaan	woun1238	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-wounaan
Americas	Eskimo-Aleut	Aleut	aleu1260	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-aleut
Americas	Eskimo-Aleut	Kalaallisut	kala1399	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-kalaallisut
Americas	Guahiboan	Cuiba	cuib1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-cuiba
Americas	Guahiboan	Guahibo	guah1255	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-guahibo
Americas	Guahiboan	Guayabero	guay1257	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-guayabero
Americas	Guahiboan	Jitnu	maca1259	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-jitnu
Americas	Guahiboan	Playero	play1240	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-playero
Americas	Huitotoan	Ocaína	ocai1244	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-ocaina
Americas	Huitotoan	Witotominica	mini1256	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotominica
Americas	Huitotoan	Witotomurui	mur1274	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotomurui
Americas	Huitotoan	Witotomipode	nupo1240	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotomipode
Americas	Jodi-Saliban	Saliba	sali1298	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-saliba
Americas	Kakua-Nukak	Kakua	cacu1241	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-kakua
Americas	Kakua-Nukak	Nukak	nuka1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-nukak
Americas	Naduhup	Jupda	hupd1244	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-jupda
Americas	Páez	Paez	paez1247	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-paez
Americas	Puinave	Puinave	puin1248	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-puinave
Americas	Quechuan	Inga	inga1252	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-inga
Americas	Tucanoan	Bara	pamo1254	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-bara
Americas	Tucanoan	Barasana	bara1380	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-barasana
Americas	Tucanoan	Carapana	cara1272	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-carapana
Americas	Tucanoan	Cubeo	cube1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-cubeo
Americas	Tucanoan	Desano	desa1247	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-desano
Americas	Tucanoan	Koreguaje	kore1283	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-koreguaje
Americas	Tucanoan	Macuna	macu1260	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-macuna
Americas	Tucanoan	Orejon	orej1242	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-orejon

Table 1: Languages in the sample (continued)

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Americas	Tucanoan	Piratapuyo	pira1254	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-piratapuyo
Americas	Tucanoan	Secoya	seco1241	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-secoya
Americas	Tucanoan	Siona	sion1247	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-siona
Americas	Tucanoan	Siriano	sirii1274	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-siriano
Americas	Tucanoan	Tanimuca	tani1257	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tanimuca
Americas	Tucanoan	Tatuyo	tatu1247	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tatuyo
Americas	Tucanoan	Tucano	tuca1252	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tucano
Americas	Tucanoan	Tuyuca	tuyu1244	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-tuyuca
Americas	Tucanoan	Waimaja	east2560	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-waimaja
Americas	Tucanoan	Wanano	guan1269	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-wanano
Americas	Tucanoan	Yuruti	yuru1263	CLICS2:lexibank-hubercolumbian-yuruti
Australia	Bunaban	Bunuba	buna1275	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bunuba
Australia	Bunaban	Gooniyandi	goon1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gooniyandi
Australia	EasternDaly	Matngele	madn1237	ausphonlex_v0-4:Matngele
Australia	Garrwan	Waanyi	wany1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Waanyi
Australia	Giimbiyu	Erre	erre1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Erre
Australia	Giimbiyu	Mengerrdji	mang1382	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mengerrdji
Australia	Giimbiyu	Urningangg	urni1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Urningangg
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Dalabon	ngal1292	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dalabon
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Gun-Djeihmi	gund1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gun-Djeihmi
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Jawoyn	djau1244	ausphonlex_v0-4:Jawoyn
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Kuninjku	mura1269	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuninjku
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Kunwinjku	guma1252	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kunwinjku
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Ngalakgan	ngal1293	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngalakgan
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Ngandi	ngan1295	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngandi
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Rembarrnga	remb1249	ausphonlex_v0-4:Rembarrnga
Australia	Gunwinyguan	Wubuy	nung1290	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wubuy
Australia	IwaidjanProper	Amurdak	amar1271	ausphonlex_v0-4:Amurdak
Australia	IwaidjanProper	Iwaidja	iwai1244	ausphonlex_v0-4:Iwaidja
Australia	IwaidjanProper	Mawng	maun1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mawng
Australia	Jarrakan	Kija	kitj1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kija
Australia	Jarrakan	Miriwoong	miri1266	ausphonlex_v0-4:Miriwoong
Australia	Laragia	Larrakia	lara1258	ausphonlex_v0-4:Larrakia
Australia	Limilngan-Wulna	Limilngan	limi1242	ausphonlex_v0-4:Limilngan
Australia	Mangarrayi-Maranoon	Alawa	alaw1244	ausphonlex_v0-4:Alawa
Australia	Mangarrayi-Maranoon	Mangarrayi	mang1381	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mangarrayi
Australia	Mangarrayi-Maranoon	Marra	mara1385	ausphonlex_v0-4:Marra
Australia	Mangarrayi-Maranoon	Warndarrang	wand1263	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warndarrang
Australia	Maningrida	Burarra	bura1267	ausphonlex_v0-4:Burarra
Australia	Maningrida	Gurr-Goni	gura1252	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gurr-Goni
Australia	Maningrida	Nakara	naka1260	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nakara
Australia	Mirndi	Gudanji	guda1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gudanji
Australia	Mirndi	Nungali	nung1291	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nungali
Australia	Mirndi	Wambaya	nucl1328	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wambaya
Australia	Nyulnyulan	Bardi	bard1255	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bardi
Australia	Nyulnyulan	Nyikina	nyig1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyikina
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Adnyamathanha	adny1235	ausphonlex_v0-4:Adnyamathanha
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Angkamuthi	angg1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Angkamuthi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Anguthimri	angu1242	ausphonlex_v0-4:Anguthimri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Atampaya	atam1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Atampaya
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ayapathu	ayab1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ayapathu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Badimaya	badil246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Badimaya
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Bakanh	paka1251	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bakanh
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Bidyara	bidy1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bidyara
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Bilinarra	bili1250	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bilinarra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Biri	biri1256	ausphonlex_v0-4:Biri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Bularnu	bula1255	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bularnu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Butchulla	baty1234	ausphonlex_v0-4:Butchulla
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Central Arrernte	mpar1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Central Arrernte
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Dhangu	dhan1270	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dhangu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Dharumbal	dhar1248	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dharumbal
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Dhay'yi	dhal1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dhay'yi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Diyari	diye1234	ausphonlex_v0-4:Diyari
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Djabugay	dyaa1242	ausphonlex_v0-4:Djabugay
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Djapu	djap1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Djapu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Djinang	djin1253	ausphonlex_v0-4:Djinang
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Duungidjawan	duun1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Duungidjawan
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Dyirbal	dyir1250	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dyirbal
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Eastern Anmatyerre	east2380	ausphonlex_v0-4:Eastern Anmatyerre
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gamilaraay	gami1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gamilaraay
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gangulu	gang1268	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gangulu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gidabal	gida1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gidabal
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gugu Badhun	gugu1253	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gugu Badhun
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gumbaynggir	kumb1268	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gumbaynggir

Table 1: Languages in the sample (continued)

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gunggari	kung1258	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gunggari
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gunya	guny1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gunya
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gupapuyngu	gupa1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gupapuyngu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Gurindji	guri1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gurindji
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Guugu Yimidhirr	gugu1255	ausphonlex_v0-4:Guugu Yimidhirr
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Guwamu	guwa1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Guwamu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ikarranggal	ikar1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ikarranggal
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Jaru	jaru1254	ausphonlex_v0-4:Jaru
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Jiwarli	djiw1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Jiwarli
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kaantju	kanj1260	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kaantju
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kalkatungu	kalk1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kalkatungu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Karajarri	kara1476	ausphonlex_v0-4:Karajarri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kariyarra	kari1304	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kariyarra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kartujarra	kart1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kartujarra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kok Nar	kokn1236	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kok Nar
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Koko Bera	gugu1254	ausphonlex_v0-4:Koko Bera
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kugu Nganhcara	wikn1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kugu Nganhcara
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kukatja	kuka1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kukatja
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kuku Yalanji	kukul273	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuku Yalanji
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kungkari	kuun1236	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kungkari
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kurrama	kurr1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kurrama
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kurtjar	gurd1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kurtjar
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Kuugu Ya'u	kuuk1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuugu Ya'u
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Linngithigh	leni1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Linngithigh
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Malkana	malg1242	ausphonlex_v0-4:Malkana
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Malngin	maln1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Malngin
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Malyangapa	maly1234	ausphonlex_v0-4:Malyangapa
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Mangala	mang1383	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mangala
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Margany	marg1253	ausphonlex_v0-4:Margany
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Martuthunira	mart1255	ausphonlex_v0-4:Martuthunira
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Mbabaram	mbab1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mbabaram
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Mirriny	kala1379	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mirriny
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Mudburra	mudb1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mudburra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Muruwari	mur1266	ausphonlex_v0-4:Muruwari
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Narrungga	naru1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Narrungga
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngaanyatjarra	ngaa1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngaanyatjarra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngadjunmaya	ngad1258	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngadjunmaya
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngalia	pitj1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngalia
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngamini	ngam1284	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngamini
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngardily	west2437	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngardily
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngarinyman	east2376	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarinyman
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngarla	ngar1296	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarla
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngarluma	ngar1287	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarluma
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngawun	ngaw1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngawun
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ngiyambaa	wang1291	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngiyambaa
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nhanda	nhan1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhanda
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nhangu	yann1237	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhangu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nhirrpi	nhir1234	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhirrpi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nukunu	nugu1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nukunu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nyamal	nyam1271	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyamal
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nyangumarta	nyan1301	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyangumarta
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nyawaygi	nyaw1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyawaygi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Nyiyaparli	nija1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyiyaparli
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ogh Angkula	ikar1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ogh Angkula
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ogh Unyjan	kawa1290	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ogh Unyjan
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Olkol	ulku1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Olkol
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Oykangand	oyka1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Oykangand
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Panyjima	pany1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Panyjima
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Payungu	bayu1240	ausphonlex_v0-4:Payungu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Pintupi	pint1250	ausphonlex_v0-4:Pintupi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Pitta Pitta	pitt1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Pitta Pitta
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Purduna	burd1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Purduna
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Putjarra	pudi1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Putjarra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Rimanggudinhma	mbar1253	ausphonlex_v0-4:Rimanggudinhma
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Ritharrngu	rita1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ritharrngu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Southern Paakintyi	darl1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Southern Paakintyi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Thalanyji	dhal1245	ausphonlex_v0-4:Thalanyji
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Tharrkari	dhar1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Tharrkari
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Thaynakwithi	tyan1235	ausphonlex_v0-4:Thaynakwithi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Thirarri	dira1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Thirarri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Umpila	umpi1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Umpila
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Waalubal	waal1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Waalubal
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Walmajarri	walm1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Walmajarri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wangkajunga	wang1288	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wangkajunga

Table 1: Languages in the sample (continued)

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wangkumara	wong1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wangkumara
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wanyjirra	wany1244	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wanyjirra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Warlmanpa	warl1255	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warlmanpa
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Warlpiri	warl1254	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warlpiri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Warluwarra	warl1256	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warluwarra
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Warnman	wanm1242	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warnman
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Warrgamay	warr1255	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warrgamay
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Warriyanga	warl1262	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warriyanga
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Watjarri	waja1257	ausphonlex_v0-4:Watjarri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wayilwan	wayi1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wayilwan
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wemba Wemba	wemb1241	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wemba Wemba
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Western Arrernte	west2441	ausphonlex_v0-4:Western Arrernte
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Western Wakaya	waga1260	ausphonlex_v0-4:Western Wakaya
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wik Mungkan	wikm1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wik Mungkan
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wiradjuri	wira1262	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wiradjuri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wirangu	wira1265	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wirangu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wiri	biril256	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wiri
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wotjobaluk	wotj1234	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wotjobaluk
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Wulguru	wulg1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wulguru
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yadhaykenu	yadh1237	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yadhaykenu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yalarnnga	yala1262	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yalarnnga
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yandruwandha	yand1253	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yandruwandha
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yanyuwa	yany1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yanyuwa
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yarluyandi	yarl1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yarluyandi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yaygir	yayg1236	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yaygir
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yidiny	yidi1250	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yidiny
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yindjibarndi	yind1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yindjibarndi
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yingkartu	ying1247	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yingkartu
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yinhawangka	yinh1234	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yinhawangka
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yintyingka	ayab1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yintyingka
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yorta Yorta	yort1237	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yorta Yorta
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yulparija	yulp1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yulparija
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yuwaalaraay	yuwa1242	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yuwaalaraay
Australia	Pama-Nyungan	Yuwaliyaay	yuwa1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yuwaliyaay
Australia	SouthernDaly	Murrinh-Patha	murr1258	ausphonlex_v0-4:Murrinh-patha
Australia	Tangkic	Lardil	lard1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Lardil
Australia	Tiwi	Tiwi	tiwi1244	ausphonlex_v0-4:Tiwi
Australia	Wadjiginy	Patjtjamalh	pung1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Patjtjamalh
Australia	Wageman	Wagiman	wage1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wagiman
Australia	WesternDaly	Emmi	amii1238	ausphonlex_v0-4:Emmi
Australia	Worrorran	Ngarinyin	ngar1284	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarinyin
Australia	Worrorran	Unggumi	ungg1243	ausphonlex_v0-4:Unggumi
Australia	Worrorran	Worrora	woro1258	ausphonlex_v0-4:Worrora
Australia	Worrorran	Yawijibaya	yawi1239	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yawijibaya
Australia	Yangmanic	Wardaman	ward1246	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wardaman
Eurasia	Abkhaz-Adyge	Abkhaz	abkh1244	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-abkhaz
Eurasia	Abkhaz-Adyge	Adyghe	adyg1241	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-adyghe
Eurasia	Afro-Asiatic	Modernhebrew	hebr1245	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-modernhebrew
Eurasia	Afro-Asiatic	Standardarabic	stan1318	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-standardarabic
Eurasia	Ainu	Hokkaidoainu	ainu1240	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-hokkaidoainu
Eurasia	Basque	Basque	basq1248	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-basque
Eurasia	Burushaski	Burushaski	buru1296	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-burushaski
Eurasia	Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Chukchi	chuk1273	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-chukchi
Eurasia	Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Itelmen	itel1242	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-itelmen
Eurasia	Dravidian	Kannada	nucl1305	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-kannada
Eurasia	Dravidian	Malayalam	mala1464	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-malayalam
Eurasia	Dravidian	Tamil	tami1289	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-tamil
Eurasia	Dravidian	Telugu	telu1262	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-telugu
Eurasia	Eskimo-Aleut	Centralsiberianyupik	cent2128	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-centralsiberianyupik
Eurasia	Indo-European	Armenian	nucl1235	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-armenian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Belarusian	bela1254	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-belarusian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Bengali	beng1280	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-bengali
Eurasia	Indo-European	Breton	bret1244	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-breton
Eurasia	Indo-European	Bulgarian	bulg1262	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-bulgarian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Catalan	stan1289	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-catalan
Eurasia	Indo-European	Croatian	croa1245	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-croatian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Czech	cec1258	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-czech
Eurasia	Indo-European	Danish	dani1285	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-danish
Eurasia	Indo-European	Dutch	dutc1256	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-dutch
Eurasia	Indo-European	English	stan1293	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-english
Eurasia	Indo-European	French	stan1290	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-french
Eurasia	Indo-European	German	stan1295	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-german
Eurasia	Indo-European	Hindi	hind1269	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-hindi
Eurasia	Indo-European	Icelandic	icel1247	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-icelandic

Table 1: Languages in the sample (*continued*)

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Eurasia	Indo-European	Irish	iris1253	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-irish
Eurasia	Indo-European	Italian	ital1282	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-italian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Latin	lati1261	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-latin
Eurasia	Indo-European	Latvian	latv1249	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-latvian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Lithuanian	lith1251	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-lithuanian
Eurasia	Indo-European	ModernGreek	mode1248	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-modernGreek
Eurasia	Indo-European	NorthernKurdish	nort2641	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernKurdish
Eurasia	Indo-European	NorthernPashto	nort2646	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernPashto
Eurasia	Indo-European	NorwegianBokmal	norw1258	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-norwegianBokmal
Eurasia	Indo-European	Ossetian	osse1243	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-ossetian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Polish	poli1260	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-polish
Eurasia	Indo-European	Portuguese	port1283	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-portuguese
Eurasia	Indo-European	Romanian	roma1327	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-romanian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Russian	russ1263	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-russian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Slovak	slov1269	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-slovak
Eurasia	Indo-European	Slovene	slov1268	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-slovene
Eurasia	Indo-European	Spanish	stan1288	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-spanish
Eurasia	Indo-European	StandardAlbanian	alba1267	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-standardAlbanian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Swedish	swed1254	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-swedish
Eurasia	Indo-European	Ukrainian	ukra1253	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-ukrainian
Eurasia	Indo-European	Welsh	wels1247	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-welsh
Eurasia	Indo-European	WesternFarsi	west2369	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-westernFarsi
Eurasia	Japonic	Japanese	nucl1643	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-japanese
Eurasia	Kartvelian	Georgian	nucl1302	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-georgian
Eurasia	Koreanic	Korean	kore1280	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-korean
Eurasia	Mongolic-Khitan	Buryat	buri1258	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-buryat
Eurasia	Mongolic-Khitan	Kalmyk	kalm1243	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-kalmyk
Eurasia	Mongolic-Khitan	Khalkhamongolian	halh1238	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-khalkhamongolian
Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian	Avar	avar1256	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-avar
Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian	Chechen	chec1245	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-chechen
Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian	Dargwa	darg1241	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-dargwa
Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian	Lak	lakk1252	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-lak
Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian	Lezgian	lezg1247	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-lezgian
Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian	Tsez	dido1241	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-tsez
Eurasia	Nivkh	Nivkh	gily1242	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-nivkh
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Beijing	beij1234	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Beijing
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Changsha	chan1326	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Changsha
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Chaozhou	chao1238	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Chaozhou
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Chengdu	chen1267	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Chengdu
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Eryuan	eryu1239	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Eryuan
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Fuzhou	fuzh1239	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Fuzhou
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Guangzhou	guan1279	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Guangzhou
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Hefei	hefe1234	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Hefei
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Heqing	heqi1238	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Heqing
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Jianchuan	jian1239	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Jianchuan
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Jinan	jina1245	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Jinan
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Kunming	kunm1234	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Kunming
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Lanping	lanp1241	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Lanping
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Luobenzhuo	nort2724	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Luobenzhuo
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	MandarinChinese	mand1415	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-mandarinChinese
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Meixian	yuet1238	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Meixian
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Nanchang	nanc1254	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Nanchang
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Qiliqiao	qili1234	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Qiliqiao
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Shenyang	shen1252	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Shenyang
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Suzhou	suzh1234	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Suzhou
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Wenzhou	ouji1238	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Wenzhou
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Xi An	xian1253	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Xi_an
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Xiamen	xiam1236	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Xiamen
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Xiangyun	xian1250	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Xiangyun
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Yangjiang	yang1307	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Yangjiang
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Yangzhou	yang1306	CLICS2:lexibank-beidasinitic-Yangzhou
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Yunlong	yunl1238	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Yunlong
Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan	Zhoucheng	zhou1234	CLICS2:lexibank-allenbai-Zhoucheng
Eurasia	Tungusic	Evenki	even1259	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-evenki
Eurasia	Tungusic	Manchu	manc1252	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-manchu
Eurasia	Tungusic	Nanai	nana1257	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-nanai
Eurasia	Turkic	Bashkir	bash1264	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-bashkir
Eurasia	Turkic	Chuvash	chuv1255	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-chuvash
Eurasia	Turkic	Kazakh	kaza1248	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-kazakh
Eurasia	Turkic	Northazerbaijani	nort2697	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northazerbaijani
Eurasia	Turkic	Northernuzbek	nort2690	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernuzbek
Eurasia	Turkic	Sakha	yaku1245	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-sakha
Eurasia	Turkic	Tatar	tata1255	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-tatar
Eurasia	Turkic	Turkish	nucl1301	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-turkish

Table 1: Languages in the sample (continued)

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Eurasia	Uralic	Erzya	erzy1239	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-erzya
Eurasia	Uralic	Estonian	esto1258	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-estonian
Eurasia	Uralic	Finnish	finn1318	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-finnish
Eurasia	Uralic	Forestenets	fore1265	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-forestenets
Eurasia	Uralic	Hillmari	west2392	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-hillmari
Eurasia	Uralic	Hungarian	hung1274	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-hungarian
Eurasia	Uralic	Inarisami	inar1241	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-inarisami
Eurasia	Uralic	Kildinsami	kild1236	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-kildinsami
Eurasia	Uralic	Komipermyak	komi1269	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-komipermyak
Eurasia	Uralic	Komizyrian	komi1268	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-komizyrian
Eurasia	Uralic	Livonian	livv1244	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-livonian
Eurasia	Uralic	Lulesami	lule1254	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-lulesami
Eurasia	Uralic	Meadowmari	east2328	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-meadowmari
Eurasia	Uralic	Moksha	moks1248	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-moksha
Eurasia	Uralic	Nganasan	ngan1291	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-nganasan
Eurasia	Uralic	Northernkhanty	khan1273	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernkhanty
Eurasia	Uralic	Northernmansi	mans1258	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernmansi
Eurasia	Uralic	Northernsami	nort2671	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernsami
Eurasia	Uralic	Northernselekup	selk1253	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernselekup
Eurasia	Uralic	Northkarelian	kare1335	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northkarelian
Eurasia	Uralic	Olonetskarelian	livv1243	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-olonetskarelian
Eurasia	Uralic	Skoltsami	skol1241	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-skoltsami
Eurasia	Uralic	Southernsami	sout2674	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-southernsami
Eurasia	Uralic	Tundranets	nene1249	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-tundranets
Eurasia	Uralic	Udmurt	udmu1245	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-udmurt
Eurasia	Uralic	Veps	veps1250	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-veps
Eurasia	Yeniseian	Ket	kett1243	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-ket
Eurasia	Yukaghir	Northernyukaghir	nort2745	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-northernyukaghir
Eurasia	Yukaghir	Southernyukaghir	sout2750	CLICS2:lexibank-northeastalex-southernyukaghir
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Amaimon	amai1246	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-amaimon
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Amele	amel1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-amele
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Anam	anam1247	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-anam
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Anamgura	anam1248	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-anamgura
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Anjam	anja1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-anjam
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Apali	apal1256	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-apali
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Arawum	araw1272	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-arawum
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Asas	asas1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-asas
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Atemble	atem1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-atemble
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Bagupi	bagu1252	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-bagupi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Baimak	baim1245	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-baimak
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Bargam	barg1252	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-bargam
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Bau	baui1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-bau
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Bepour	bepo1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-bepour
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Bilakura	bila1257	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-bilakura
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Biyom	biyo1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-biyom
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Bongu	bong1291	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-bongu
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Brem	brem1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-brem
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Danaru	dana1254	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-danaru
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Faita	fait1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-faita
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Gal	gall1278	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-gal
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Ganglau	gang1270	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-ganglau
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Garus	garu1246	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-garus
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Gavak	dimi1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-gavak
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Girawa	gira1247	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-girawa
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Gumalu	guma1255	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-gumalu
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Isabi	isab1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-isabi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Isebe	iseb1246	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-isebe
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Jilim	jili1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-jilim
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Kare	kare1341	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-kare
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Kein	kein1239	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-kein
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Kesawai	kesa1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-kesawai
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Kobol	kobo1248	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-kobol
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Korak	kora1296	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-korak
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Kowaki	kowa1245	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-kowaki
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Lemio	lemi1243	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-lemio
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Maia-Pila	pila1246	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-maia-pila
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Mala	mala1494	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-mala
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Malas	mala1495	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-malas
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Male	male1291	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-male
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Matepi	mate1260	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-matepi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Mauwake	mauw1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-mauwake
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Mawak	mawa1266	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-mawak
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Mawan	mawa1267	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-mawan
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Miani	mian1254	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-miani

Table 1: Languages in the sample (continued)

Macro-area	Family	Language	Glottocode	Name in database
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Migum	kolo1267	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-migum
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Moere	moer1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-moere
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Moresada	more1258	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-moresada
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Mosimo	mosi1248	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-mosimo
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Mum	mumm1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-mum
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Munit	muni1257	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-munit
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Murupi	muru1273	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-murupi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Musak	musu1266	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-musak
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Musar	musu1265	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-musar
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Nake	nake1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-nake
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Nend	nend1239	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-nend
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Nobonob	nobo1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-nobonob
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Ogea	ogea1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-ogea
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Pal	pall1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-pal
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Pamosu	pamo1253	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-pamosu
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Panim	pani1258	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-panim
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Paynamar	payn1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-paynamar
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Pulabu	pula1267	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-pulabu
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Rapting	rapt1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-rapting
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Rempi	remp1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-rempi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Rerau	rera1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-rerau
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Saep	saep1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-saep
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sam	samm1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sam
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Samosa	samo1306	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-samosa
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Saruga	saru1243	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-saruga
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sausi	sau1246	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sausi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sihan	siha1245	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sihan
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sileibi	sile1255	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sileibi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Silopi	silo1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-silopi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sinsauru	sins1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sinsauru
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Siroi	siro1249	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-siroi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sop	sopp1247	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sop
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Sumau	suma1270	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-sumau
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Tauya	tauy1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-tauya
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Ukuriguma	ukur1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-ukuriguma
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Urigina	urig1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-urigina
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Usan	usan1239	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-usan
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Utarmbung	utar1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-utarmbung
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Utu	utu1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-utu
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Uya	uyaa1238	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-uya
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Uyajitaya	dudu1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-uyajitaya
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Wadaginam	wada1263	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-wadaginam
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Wagi	wagi1249	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-wagi
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Wamas	wama1247	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-wamas
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Wanambre	wana1269	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-wanambre
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Waskia	wask1241	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-waskia
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Watiwa	dump1243	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-watiwa
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Waube	kwat1244	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-waube
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Yaben	yabe1255	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-yaben
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Yabong	yabo1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-yabong
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Yangulam	yang1298	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-yangulam
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Yarawata	yara1250	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-yarawata
Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea	Yoidik	yoid1240	CLICS2:lexibank-zraggenmadang-yoidik
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Abui	abui1241	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-abui
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Adang	adan1251	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-adang
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Alorpantar	alor1249	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-alorpantar
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Blagar	blag1240	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-blagar
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Kaera	kaer1234	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-kaera
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Kamang	kama1365	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-kamang
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Klon	kelo1247	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-klon
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Kui	kuii1254	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-kui
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Nedebang	nede1245	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-nedebang
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Sawila	sawi1256	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-sawila
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Teiwa	teiw1235	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-teiwa
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Wersing	wers1238	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-wersing
Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Westernpantar	lamm1241	CLICS2:lexibank-robinsonap-westernpantar

2 SSP violations in onsets

SSP violations within word-initial onsets in 496 languages are tabulated in Table 2. Languages are ordered alphabetically by name. Columns display the presence (1) or absence (0) of violations due to all satellites (All), or due to sibilant (Sib), nasal (Nas), approximant (Appr) or non-sibilant obstruent (Obs) satellites, according to the split and merged methods. This information is also available in the files `violations_satellites_merged.tsv` and `violations_satellites_split.tsv`.

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Abkhaz (abkh1244)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Abui (abui1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Achagua (acha1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adang (adan1251)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adnyamathanha (adny1235)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adyghe (adyg1241)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Alawa (alaw1244)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aleut (aleu1260)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Alorpantar (alor1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amaimon (amai1246)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amele (amel1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amurdak (amar1271)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anam (anam1247)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Anangura (anam1248)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Angkamuthi (angg1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anguthimri (angu1242)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anjam (anja1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Apali (apal1256)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arawum (araw1272)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Armenian (nucl1235)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Asas (asas1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atampaya (atam1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atemble (atem1241)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Avar (avar1256)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Awa (awac1239)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ayapathu (ayab1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Badimaya (badi1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bagupi (bagu1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Baimak (baim1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bakanh (paka1251)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Baniva (bani1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bara (pamo1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Barasana (bara1380)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bardi (bard1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bargam (barg1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bari (bari1297)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Bashkir (bash1264)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Basque (basq1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bau (bauu1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beijing (beij1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Belarusian (bela1254)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Bengali (beng1280)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Bepour (bepo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bidyara (bidy1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bilakura (bila1257)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Bilinarra (bili1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Biri (biri1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Biyom (biyo1244)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Blagar (blag1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bongu (bong1291)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Bora (nucl1660)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Brem (brem1238)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Breton (bret1244)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Bularnu (bula1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bulgarian (bulg1262)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Bunuba (buna1275)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Burarra (bura1267)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Burushaski (buru1296)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Buryat (buri1258)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Butchulla (baty1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cabiyari (cabi1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carapana (cara1272)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carijona (cari1279)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Catalan (stan1289)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Catio (embe1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Central Arrernte (mpar1238)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Centralsiberian yupik (cent2128)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Changsha (chan1326)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaozhou (chao1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chapalaachi (chac1249)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Chechen (chec1245)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Chengdu (chen1267)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chimila (chim1309)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chukchi (chuk1273)	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Chuvash (chuv1255)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Croatian (croa1245)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Cubeo (cube1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cuiba (cuib1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Curripaco (curr1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Czech (czec1258)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Dalabon (ngal1292)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Danaru (dana1254)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Danish (dani1285)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dargwa (darg1241)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Desano (desa1247)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Dhangu (dhan1270)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dharumbal (dhar1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dhay'yi (dhal1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dimina (mala1522)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diyari (diye1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Djabugay (dyaa1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Djapu (djap1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Djinang (djin1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dutch (dutc1256)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Duungidjawan (duun1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dyirbal (dyir1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Eastern Anmatyerre (east2380)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Emberachami (embe1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Emberadarien (nort2972)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Emberatado (embe1261)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Emmi (amii1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
English (stan1293)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Epenabasurudo (basu1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Epenasaija (basu1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Erre (erre1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Eryuan (eryu1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Erzya (erzy1239)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Estonian (esto1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Evenki (even1259)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Faita (fait1240)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Finnish (finn1318)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Forestenets (fore1265)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
French (stan1290)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Fuzhou (fuzh1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gal (gall1278)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gamilaraay (gami1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ganglau (gang1270)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Gangulu (gang1268)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Garus (garu1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gavak (dimil244)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Georgian (nucl1302)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
German (stan1295)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Giacone (peri1265)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Gidabal (gida1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Girawa (giral247)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gooniyandi (goon1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guahibo (guah1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guambiano (guam1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guangzhou (guan1279)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guayabero (guay1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gudanji (guda1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gugu Badhun (gugu1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gumalu (guma1255)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gumbaynggir (kumb1268)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gun-Djeihmi (gund1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gunggari (kung1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gunya (guny1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gupapuyngu (gupa1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gurindji (guri1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gurr-Goni (gura1252)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guugu Yimidhirr (gugu1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guwamu (guwa1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hefei (hefei1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Heqing (heqi1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hillmari (west2392)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Hindi (hind1269)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Hokkaidoainu (ainu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hungarian (hung1274)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Icelandic (icel1247)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Ika (arhu1242)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ikarranggal (ikar1243)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Inarisami (inar1241)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Inga (inga1252)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Irish (iris1253)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Isabi (isab1240)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Isebe (iseb1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Italian (ital1282)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Itelmen (itel1242)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Iwaidja (iwai1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Japanese (nucl1643)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jaru (jaru1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jawoyn (djau1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jianchuan (jian1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jilim (jili1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jinan (jina1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jitnu (maca1259)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jiwarli (djiw1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jupda (hupd1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kaantju (kanj1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kaera (kaer1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kakua (cacu1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kalaallisut (kala1399)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Kalkatungu (kalk1246)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kalmyk (kalm1243)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Kamang (kama1365)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kamsa (cams1241)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Kannada (nucl1305)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Karajarri (kara1476)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kare (kare1341)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kariyarra (kari1304)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kartujarra (kart1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kazakh (kaza1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kein (kein1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kesawai (kesa1244)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Ket (kett1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Khalkhamongolian (halh1238)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Kija (kitj1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kildinsami (kild1236)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Klon (kelo1247)	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Kobol (kobo1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kogui (cogu1240)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Kok Nar (kokn1236)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Koko Bera (gugu1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Komipermyak (komi1269)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Komizyrian (komi1268)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Korak (kora1296)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Korean (kore1280)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Koreguaje (kore1283)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kowaki (kowa1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kugu Nganhcara (wikn1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kui (kuui1254)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Kukatja (kuka1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kuku Yalanji (kuku1273)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kungkari (kuun1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Kuninjku (mura1269)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kunming (kunm1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kunwinjku (guma1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kurrama (kurr1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kurtjar (gurd1238)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Kuugu Ya'u (kuuk1238)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lak (lakk1252)	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Lanping (lanp1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lardil (lard1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larrakia (lara1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latin (lati1261)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Latvian (latv1249)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Lemio (lemi1243)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Lezgian (lezg1247)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Limilngan (limi1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Linngithigh (leni1238)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lithuanian (lith1251)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Livonian (livv1244)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Lulesami (lule1254)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Luobenzhuo (nort2724)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Macuna (macu1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maia-Pila (pila1246)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mala (mala1494)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malas (mala1495)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malayalam (mala1464)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Male (male1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malkana (malg1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malngin (maln1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malyangapa (maly1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Manchu (manc1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mandarinchinese (mand1415)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mangala (mang1383)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mangarrayi (mang1381)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Margany (marg1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Marra (mara1385)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Martuthunira (mart1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Matepi (mate1260)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Matngele (madn1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mauwake (mauw1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mawak (mawa1266)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mawan (mawa1267)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mawng (maun1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mbabaram (mbab1239)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meadowmari (east2328)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Meixian (yuet1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mengerrdji (mang1382)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Miani (mian1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Migum (kolo1267)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Mirana (mira1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Miriwoong (miri1266)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mirniny (kala1379)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moderngreek (mode1248)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Modernhebrew (hebr1245)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Moere (moer1240)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moksha (moks1248)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Moresada (more1258)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Mosimo (mosi1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mudburra (mudb1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Muinane (muin1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mum (mumm1238)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Munit (muni1257)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Murrinh-Patha (murr1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Murupi (muru1273)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Muruwari (muru1266)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Musak (musa1266)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Musar (musa1265)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nakara (naka1260)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Nake (nake1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nanai (nana1257)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Nanchang (nanc1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Narrungga (naru1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nedebang (nede1245)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Nend (nend1239)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Ngaanyatjarra (ngaa1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngadjunmaya (ngad1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngalakgan (ngal1293)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngalia (pitj1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngamini (ngam1284)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nganasan (ngan1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngandi (ngan1295)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngardily (west2437)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarinyin (ngar1284)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarinyman (east2376)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarla (ngar1296)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarluma (ngar1287)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngawun (ngaw1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngiyambaa (wang1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nhanda (nhan1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nhangu (yann1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nhirrpi (nhir1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nivkh (gily1242)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Nobonob (nobo1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Northzerbaijani (nort2697)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Northernkhanty (khan1273)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Northernkurdish (nort2641)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Northernmansi (mans1258)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Northernpashto (nort2646)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Northernsami (nort2671)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Northernselkup (selk1253)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Northernuzbek (nort2690)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Northernyukaghir (nort2745)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Northkarelian (kare1335)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Norwegianbokmal (norw1258)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Nukak (nuka1242)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nukunu (nugu1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nungali (nung1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Nyamal (nyam1271)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyangumarta (nyan1301)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyawaygi (nyaw1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyikina (nyig1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyiyaparli (nija1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ocaina (ocai1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogea (ogea1238)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Ogh Angkula (ikar1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogh Unyjan (kawa1290)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Olkol (ulku1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Olonetskarelian (livv1243)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Orejon (orej1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ossetian (osse1243)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Oykangand (oyka1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez (paez1247)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Pal (pall1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pamosu (pamo1253)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panim (pani1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panyjima (pany1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Patjtjamalh (pung1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paynamar (payn1244)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Payungu (bayu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Piapoco (piap1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pintupi (pint1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Piratapuyo (pira1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pitta Pitta (pitt1247)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Playero (play1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Polish (poli1260)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Portuguese (port1283)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Puinave (puin1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pulabu (pula1267)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Purduna (burd1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Putijarra (pudi1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Qiliqiao (qili1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rapting (rapt1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rembarrnga (remb1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rempi (remp1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rerau (rera1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resigaro (resi1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rimanggudinhma (mbar1253)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Ritharrngu (rita1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Romanian (roma1327)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Russian (russ1263)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Saep (saep1240)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sakha (yaku1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saliba (sali1298)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sam (samm1244)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Samosa (samo1306)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saruga (saru1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sausi (saus1246)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Sawila (sawil1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Secoya (seco1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Shenyang (shen1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Sihan (siha1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sileibi (sile1255)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Silopi (silo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sinsauru (sins1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Siona (sion1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Siriano (siri1274)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Siroi (siro1249)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Skoltsami (skoll1241)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Slovak (slov1269)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Slovene (slov1268)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Sop (sopp1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Southern Paakintyi (dar11243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Southernsami (sout2674)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Southern Yukaghir (sout2750)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spanish (stan1288)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Standard Albanian (alba1267)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Standard Arabic (stan1318)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Sumau (suma1270)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suzhou (suzh1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Swedish (swed1254)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Tamil (tami1289)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tanimuca (tani1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tariano (peri1265)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tatar (tata1255)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Tatuyo (tatu1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tauya (tauy1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Teiwa (teiw1235)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Telugu (telu1262)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Thalanyji (dhal1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tharrkari (dhar1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Thaynakwithi (tyan1235)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Thirarri (dira1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tiwi (tiwi1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Totoro (toto1306)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tsafikiqipila (colo1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tsez (dido1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tucano (tuca1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tundranenets (nene1249)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Tunecentral (cent2150)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Turkish (nucl1301)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tuyuca (tuyu1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Udmurt (udmu1245)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Ukrainian (ukra1253)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Ukuriguma (ukur1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Umpila (umpi1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unggumi (ungg1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Urigina (urigi1240)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Urningang (urni1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Usan (usan1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Utarmbung (utar1238)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Utu (utuu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Uya (uyaa1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Uyajitaya (dudu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Veps (veps1250)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Waalubal (waal1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waanyi (wany1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wadaginam (wada1263)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Wagi (wagi1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wagiman (wage1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waimaja (east2560)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Walmajarri (walm1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wamas (wama1247)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wambaya (nucl1328)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wanambre (wana1269)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wanano (guan1269)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wangkajunga (wang1288)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wangkumara (wong1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wanyjirra (wany1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wardaman (ward1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warlmanpa (warl1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warlpiri (warl1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warluwarra (warl1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warndarrang (wand1263)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warnman (wanm1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warrgamay (warr1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warriyanga (wari1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waskia (wask1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Watiwa (dump1243)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Watjarri (waja1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waube (kwat1244)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Wayilwan (wayi1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wayuu (wayu1243)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Welsh (wels1247)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Wemba Wemba (wemb1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wenzhou (ouji1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wersing (wers1238)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Western Arrernte (west2441)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Western Wakaya (waga1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Westernfarsi (west2369)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Westernpantar (lamm1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wik Mungkan (wikm1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wiradjuri (wira1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wirangu (wira1265)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wiri (biri1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Witotominica (mini1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Witotomurui (muru1274)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Witotnipode (nupo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Worrorra (woro1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wotjobaluk (wotj1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wounaan (woun1238)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Wubuy (nung1290)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wulguru (wulg1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Xi An (xian1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Xiamen (xiam1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Xiangyun (xian1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yaben (yabel1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2: SSP violations in onsets (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Yabong (yabo1240)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadhaykenu (yadh1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yalarnnga (yala1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yandruwandha (yand1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yangjiang (yang1307)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yangulam (yang1298)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yangzhou (yang1306)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yanyuwa (yany1243)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Yarawata (yara1250)	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yarluyandi (yar1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yawijibaya (yaw1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yaygir (yayg1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yidiny (yidi1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yindjibarndi (yind1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yingkarta (ying1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yinhawangka (yinh1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yintyinka (ayab1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yoidik (yoid1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yorta Yorta (yort1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yucuna (yucu1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yukpa (yukp1241)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Yulparija (yulp1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yunlong (yunl1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuruti (yuru1263)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuwaalaraay (yuwa1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuwaliyaay (yuwa1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Zhoucheng (zhou1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

3 SSP violations in codas

SSP violations within word-final codas in 496 languages are tabulated in Table 3. Languages are ordered alphabetically by name. Columns display the presence (1) or absence (0) of violations due to all satellites (All), or due to sibilant (Sib), nasal (Nas), approximant (Appr) or non-sibilant obstruent (Obs) satellites, according to the split and merged methods. This information is also available in the files `violations_satellites_merged.tsv` and `violations_satellites_split.tsv`.

Table 3: SSP violations in codas

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Abkhaz (abkh1244)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Abui (abui1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Achagua (acha1250)	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Adang (adan1251)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Adnyamathanha (adny1235)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adyghe (adyg1241)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Alawa (alaw1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aleut (aleu1260)	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
Alorpantar (alor1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amaimon (amai1246)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Amele (amel1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amurdak (amar1271)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anam (anam1247)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Anangura (anam1248)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Angkamuthi (angg1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anguthimri (angu1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anjam (anja1238)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Apali (apal1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Arawum (araw1272)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Armenian (nucl1235)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Asas (asas1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atampaya (atam1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atemble (atem1241)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Avar (avar1256)	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0
Awa (awac1239)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Ayapathu (ayab1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Badimaya (badi1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bagupi (bagu1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Baimak (baim1245)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Bakanh (paka1251)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Baniva (bani1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bara (pamo1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Barasana (bara1380)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bardi (bard1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bargam (barg1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bari (bari1297)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bashkir (bash1264)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Basque (basq1248)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bau (bauu1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beijing (beij1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Belarusian (bela1254)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Bengali (beng1280)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bepour (bepo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bidyara (bidy1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bilakura (bila1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Bilinarra (bili1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Biri (biri1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Biyom (biyo1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Blagar (blag1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bongu (bong1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bora (nucl1660)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brem (brem1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Breton (bret1244)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Bularnu (bula1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bulgarian (bulg1262)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bunuba (buna1275)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Burarra (bura1267)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Burushaski (buru1296)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Buryat (buri1258)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Butchulla (baty1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cabiyari (cabi1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carapana (cara1272)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carijona (cari1279)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Catalan (stan1289)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Catio (embe1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Central Arrernte (mpar1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Centralsiberian yupik (cent2128)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Changsha (chan1326)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaozhou (chao1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chapalaachi (chac1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chechen (chec1245)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Chengdu (chen1267)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chimila (chim1309)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chukchi (chuk1273)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chuvash (chuv1255)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Croatian (croa1245)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cubeo (cube1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cuiba (cuib1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Curripaco (curr1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Czech (czec1258)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Dalabon (ngal1292)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Danaru (dana1254)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Danish (dani1285)	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Dargwa (darg1241)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Desano (desa1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dhangu (dhan1270)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dharumbal (dhar1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dhay'yi (dhal1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dimina (mala1522)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diyari (diye1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Djabugay (dyaa1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Djapu (djap1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Djinang (djin1253)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dutch (dutc1256)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Duungidjawan (duun1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dyirbal (dyir1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Eastern Anmatyerre (east2380)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Emberachami (embe1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Emberadarien (nort2972)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Emberatado (embe1261)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Emmi (amii1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
English (stan1293)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Epenabasurudo (basu1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Epenasaija (basu1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Erre (erre1238)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Eryuan (eryu1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Erzya (erzy1239)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Estonian (esto1258)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Evenki (even1259)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Faita (fait1240)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Finnish (finn1318)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Forestenets (fore1265)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
French (stan1290)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fuzhou (fuzh1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gal (gall1278)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gamilaraay (gami1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ganglau (gang1270)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Gangulu (gang1268)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Garus (garu1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gavak (dimil244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Georgian (nucl1302)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
German (stan1295)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
Giacone (peri1265)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Gidabal (gida1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Girawa (giral247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gooniyandi (goon1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guahibo (guah1255)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Guambiano (guam1248)	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Guangzhou (guan1279)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guayabero (guay1257)	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
Gudanji (guda1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gugu Badhun (gugu1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gumalu (guma1255)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Gumbaynggir (kumb1268)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gun-Djehmi (gund1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gunggari (kung1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gunya (guny1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gupapuyngu (gupa1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gurindji (guri1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gurr-Goni (gura1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guugu Yimidhirr (gugu1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guwamu (guwa1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hefei (hefe1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Heqing (heqi1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hillmari (west2392)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Hindi (hind1269)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Hokkaidoainu (ainu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hungarian (hung1274)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Icelandic (icel1247)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Ika (arhu1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ikarranggal (ikar1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Inarisami (inar1241)	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Inga (inga1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Irish (iris1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Isabi (isab1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Isebe (iseb1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Italian (ital1282)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Itelmen (itel1242)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Iwaidja (iwai1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Japanese (nucl1643)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jaru (jaru1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jawoyn (djau1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jianchuan (jian1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jilim (jili1241)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Jinan (jina1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jitnu (maca1259)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jiwarli (djiw1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jupda (hupd1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kaantju (kanj1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kaera (kaer1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kakua (cacu1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kalaallisut (kala1399)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kalkatungu (kalk1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kalmyk (kalm1243)	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Kamang (kama1365)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kamsa (cams1241)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kannada (nucl1305)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karajarri (kara1476)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kare (kare1341)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kariyarra (kari1304)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kartujarra (kart1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kazakh (kaza1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kein (kein1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kesawai (kesa1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ket (kett1243)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Khalkhamongolian (halh1238)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kija (kitj1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kildinsami (kild1236)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Klon (kelo1247)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Kobol (kobo1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kogui (cogu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kok Nar (kokn1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Koko Bera (gugu1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Komipermyak (komi1269)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Komizyrian (komi1268)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Korak (kora1296)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Korean (kore1280)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
Koreguaje (kore1283)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kowaki (kowa1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kugu Nganhcara (wikn1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kui (kuui1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kukatja (kuka1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kuku Yalanji (kuku1273)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kungkari (kuun1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Kuninjku (mura1269)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kunming (kunm1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kunwinjku (guma1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kurrama (kurr1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kurtjar (gurd1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kuugu Ya'u (kuuk1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lak (lakk1252)	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
Lanping (lanp1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lardil (lard1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larrakia (lara1258)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Latin (lati1261)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Latvian (latv1249)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Lemio (lemi1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lezgian (lezg1247)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Limilngan (limi1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Linngithigh (leni1238)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Lithuanian (lith1251)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Livonian (livv1244)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Lulesami (lule1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Luobenzhuo (nort2724)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Macuna (macu1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maia-Pila (pila1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mala (mala1494)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malas (mala1495)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Malayalam (mala1464)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Male (male1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malkana (malg1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malngin (maln1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malyangapa (maly1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Manchu (manc1252)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Mandarinchinese (mand1415)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Mangala (mang1383)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mangarrayi (mang1381)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Margany (marg1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Marra (mara1385)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Martuthunira (mart1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Matepi (mate1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Matngele (madn1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mauwake (mauw1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mawak (mawa1266)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mawan (mawa1267)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mawng (maun1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mbabaram (mbab1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meadowmari (east2328)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Meixian (yuet1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mengerrdji (mang1382)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Miani (mian1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Migum (kolo1267)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Mirana (mira1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Miriwoong (miri1266)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Mirniny (kala1379)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moderngreek (mode1248)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Modernhebrew (hebr1245)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Moere (moer1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moksha (moks1248)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
Moresada (more1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mosimo (mosi1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mudburra (mudb1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Muinane (muin1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mum (mumm1238)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Munit (muni1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Murrinh-Patha (murr1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Murupi (muru1273)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Muruwari (muru1266)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Musak (musa1266)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Musar (musa1265)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nakara (naka1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nake (nake1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nanai (nana1257)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Nanchang (nanc1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Narrungga (naru1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nedebang (nede1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nend (nend1239)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Ngaanyatjarra (ngaa1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngadjunmaya (ngad1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngalakgan (ngal1293)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngalia (pitj1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngamini (ngam1284)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nganasan (ngan1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngandi (ngan1295)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngardily (west2437)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarinyin (ngar1284)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarinyman (east2376)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarla (ngar1296)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngarluma (ngar1287)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngawun (ngaw1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ngiyambaa (wang1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nhanda (nhan1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nhangu (yann1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nhirrpi (nhir1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nivkh (gily1242)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Nobonob (nobo1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Northzerbaijani (nort2697)	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Northernkhanty (khan1273)	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
Northernkurdish (nort2641)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Northernmansi (mans1258)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Northernpashto (nort2646)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Northernsami (nort2671)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Northernselkup (selk1253)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Northernuzbek (nort2690)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Northernyukaghir (nort2745)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Northkarelian (kare1335)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Norwegianbokmal (norw1258)	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
Nukak (nuka1242)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Nukunu (nugu1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nungali (nung1291)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Nyamal (nyam1271)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyangumarta (nyan1301)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyawaygi (nyaw1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nyikina (nyig1240)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Nyiyaparli (nija1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ocaina (ocai1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogea (ogea1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogh Angkula (ikar1243)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Ogh Unyjan (kawa1290)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Olkol (ulku1238)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
Olonetskarelian (livv1243)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Orejon (orej1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ossetian (osse1243)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Oykangand (oyka1239)	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
Paez (paez1247)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Pal (pall1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pamosu (pamo1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panim (pani1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panyjima (pany1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Patjtjamalh (pung1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paynamar (payn1244)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Payungu (bayu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Piapoco (piap1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pintupi (pint1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Piratapuyo (pira1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pitta Pitta (pitt1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Playero (play1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Polish (poli1260)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Portuguese (port1283)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Puinave (puin1248)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pulabu (pula1267)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Purduna (burd1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Putijarra (pudi1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Qiliqiao (qili1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rapting (rapt1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rembarrnga (remb1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rempi (remp1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rerau (rera1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resigaro (resi1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rimanggudinhma (mbar1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ritharrngu (rita1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Romanian (roma1327)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Russian (russ1263)	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Saep (saep1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sakha (yaku1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saliba (sali1298)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sam (samm1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Samosa (samo1306)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saruga (saru1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sausi (saus1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sawila (sawil1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Secoya (seco1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Shenyang (shen1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Sihan (siha1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sileibi (sile1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Silopi (silo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sinsauru (sins1241)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Siona (sion1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Siriano (siri1274)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Siroi (siro1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Skoltsami (skoll1241)	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
Slovak (slov1269)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Slovene (slov1268)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Sop (sopp1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Southern Paakintyi (dar11243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Southernsami (sout2674)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Southernyukaghir (sout2750)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spanish (stan1288)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Standardalbanian (alba1267)	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Standardarabic (stan1318)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Sumau (suma1270)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suzhou (suzh1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Swedish (swed1254)	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Tamil (tami1289)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tanimuca (tani1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tariano (peri1265)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tatar (tata1255)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tatuyo (tatu1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tauya (tauy1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Teiwa (teiw1235)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Telugu (telu1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Thalanyji (dhal1245)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tharrkari (dhar1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Thaynakwithi (tyan1235)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Thirarri (dira1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tiwi (tiwi1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Totoro (toto1306)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tsafiquipila (colo1256)	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Tsez (dido1241)	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Tucano (tuca1252)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tundranenets (nene1249)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Tunecentral (cent2150)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turkish (nucl1301)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tuyuca (tuyu1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Udmurt (udmu1245)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Ukrainian (ukra1253)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ukuriguma (ukur1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Umpila (umpi1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unggumi (ungg1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Urigina (urigi1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Urningangg (urni1239)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Usan (usan1239)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Utarmbung (utar1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Utu (utuu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Uya (uyaa1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Uyajitaya (dudu1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Veps (veps1250)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Waalubal (waal1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waanyi (wany1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wadaginam (wada1263)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Wagi (wagi1249)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wagiman (wage1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waimaja (east2560)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Walmajarri (walm1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wamas (wama1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wambaya (nucl1328)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wanambre (wana1269)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wanano (guan1269)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wangkajunga (wang1288)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wangkumara (wong1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wanyjirra (wany1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wardaman (ward1246)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warlmanpa (warl1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warlpiri (warl1254)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warluwarra (warl1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warndarrang (wand1263)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warnman (wanm1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warrgamay (warr1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Warriyanga (wari1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waskia (wask1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Watiwa (dump1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Watjarri (waja1257)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waube (kwat1244)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wayilwan (wayi1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wayuu (wayu1243)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Welsh (wels1247)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Wemba Wemba (wemb1241)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Wenzhou (ouji1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wersing (wers1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Western Arrernte (west2441)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Western Wakaya (waga1260)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Westernfarsi (west2369)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Westernpantar (lamm1241)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wik Mungkan (wikm1247)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Wiradjuri (wira1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wirangu (wira1265)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wiri (biri1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Witotominica (mini1256)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Witotomurui (muru1274)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Witotnipode (nupo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Worrorra (woro1258)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wotjobaluk (wotj1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wounaan (woun1238)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Wubuy (nung1290)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wulguru (wulg1239)	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Xi An (xian1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Xiamen (xiam1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Xiangyun (xian1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yaben (yabel1255)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: SSP violations in codas (*continued*)

Language	Split Method					Merged Method				
	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs	All	Sib	Nas	Appr	Obs
Yabong (yabo1240)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadhaykenu (yadh1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yalarnnga (yala1262)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yandruwandha (yand1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yangjiang (yang1307)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Yangulam (yang1298)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yangzhou (yang1306)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yanyuwa (yany1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yarawata (yara1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yarluyandi (yar1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yawijibaya (yaw1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yaygir (yayg1236)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yidiny (yidi1250)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yindjibarndi (yind1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yingkarta (ying1247)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yinhawangka (yinh1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yintyingka (ayab1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yoidik (yoid1240)	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Yorta Yorta (yort1237)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yucuna (yucu1253)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yukpa (yukp1241)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yulparija (yulp1239)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yunlong (yunl1238)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuruti (yuru1263)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuwaalaraay (yuwa1242)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yuwaliyaay (yuwa1243)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Zhoucheng (zhou1234)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

4 Calculation of genealogically-sensitive proportions

The quantitative investigation of cross-linguistic variation is inherently complicated by the fact that languages are related, genealogically and areally. Typologists have mostly managed this problem by constructing balanced samples (Dryer 1989), by choosing at most one language from each language family (or from some relatively deep-time subgroup), however this places severe limits the number of languages we can investigate, especially in a study of this kind where digitised datasets are used. Here we use an alternative method of taking genealogical relatedness into account, introduced by Macklin-Cordes & Round (2022).

In the present study, our results are often in the form of a proportion of languages that exhibit some kind of SSP-violation. In the main paper we report genealogically-sensitive proportions, i.e., proportions which take genealogical relatedness into account by assigning differential weights to languages in such a way that languages with many close relatives in the dataset count less and those with few close relatives in the dataset count more. We do this using the ‘BranchManager’ method (Stone & Sidow 2007) recommend by Macklin-Cordes & Round (2022). Calculating genealogically-sensitive proportions requires a tree of languages, which encapsulates hypotheses about the languages’ degrees of relatedness. For family-internal hypotheses, we use genealogical data from glottolog.com version 4.2 (Hammarström et al. 2020). For between-family relatedness, Macklin-Cordes & Round (2022) argue that in traditional balanced samples, language families are treated as ‘independent’ in a manner which is equivalent to combining them in a tree whose root splits directly to all families, in a broad ‘rake’ structure. Taking a conservative approach, we do this too, except that we also group families within Dryer’s (1989) large linguistic areas.

The tree and the phylogenetic weights used for calculating genealogically-sensitive proportions in this study were obtained using the `glottoTrees` (Round 2021a) and `phyloWeights` (Round 2021b) packages, using the following code in R (R Core Team 2021), following supplementary section S2 of Macklin-Cordes & Round (2022). The resulting tree is shown in Figure 1. The proportions themselves are reported in Section 5.

To install `glottoTrees` and `phyloWeights`:

```
install.packages("devtools")
library(devtools)
install_github("erichround/phyloWeights")
install_github("erichround/glottoTrees")
```

```
# Load packages
library(phyloWeights)
library(glottoTrees)
library(tidyverse)
library(ape)

# Load the data and format it
metadata <- read_tsv("data/language_metadata.tsv")
dat_mg <- read_tsv("data/violations_satellites_merged_Jun_2022.tsv")
dat_sp <- read_tsv("data/violations_satellites_split_Jun_2022.tsv")
colnames(dat_mg)[-1] <- paste0(colnames(dat_mg)[-1], "_mg")
colnames(dat_sp)[-1] <- paste0(colnames(dat_sp)[-1], "_sp")
dat <-
  metadata %>%
  select(glottocode, name, doculect) %>%
  left_join(dat_mg, by = "doculect") %>%
  left_join(dat_sp, by = "doculect") %>%
  rename(tip = glottocode) %>%
  arrange(tip)

# The tree was constructed from a glottolog supertree, making use of glottolog's
# macroareas. Since the language sample covered relatively few families in the
```

```

# Americas, a single group was used for South America and North America.
# Additionally, the only African language available in the sample was Arabic, so
# Africa and Eurasia were grouped together,
macros <- list(c("South America", "North America"), c("Africa", "Eurasia"),
              "Papunesia", "Australia")

supertree <-
  assemble_supertree(macro_groups = macros, glottolog_version = "4.2") %>%
  abridge_labels()

# Five tips were cloned, in cases where we had data for two varieties
# corresponding to just one tip in the glottolog supertree:
doubles <- c("ayab1239", "basul1242", "biri1256", "ikar1243", "peri1265")
supertree <-
  supertree %>%
  clone_tip(subgroup = TRUE, label = doubles) %>%
  apply_duplicate_suffixes()
newdoubles <- supertree$tip.label[str_sub(supertree$tip.label, 1, 8) %in% doubles]
dat$tip[dat$tip %in% doubles] <- newdoubles

# Eight tips were added, in case where for sister lects (A,B), glottolog placed
# A as a node above B. In such cases, in new tip A was placed below the existing
# glottolog node A:
nodes_to_add_as_tips <- c("alor1249", "gami1243", "guri1247", "mand1415",
                        "sins1241", "wang1291", "warl1254", "yand1253")
for (node_i in nodes_to_add_as_tips) {
  supertree <- add_tip(supertree, label = node_i, parent_label = node_i)
}

# From this supertree, the 496 languages in our dataset were kept. The internal
# node `mada1298` was collapsed, as were all non-branching internal nodes:
supertree <-
  supertree %>%
  keep_as_tip(label = dat$tip) %>%
  collapse_node(label = "mada1298")
supertree <-
  supertree %>%
  collapse_node(label = nonbranching_nodes(supertree)) %>%

# Finally, branch lengths were assigned. Branches were first assigned
# exponential lengths. Then, in order to diminish the importance of the macro
# groups, the branches above them were shortened to a length of 1/40. The effect
# of this decision is that the implied distance between families in different
# macro groups is only marginally greater than between families within a single
# macro group.
rescale_branches_exp() %>%
rescale_deepest_branches(1/40)

# For plotting, relabel the tree tips with regular language names rather than
# glottocodes.
supertree2 <- supertree
supertree2$tip.label <- dat$name[match(supertree$tip.label, dat$tip)]

```

```

# Plot the tree as in Figure 1.
plot(ladderize(supertree2, right = FALSE), type = "fan",
     cex = 0.3, label.offset = 0.002, edge.width = 0.5)

# Genealogically-sensitive proportions are calculated as weighted averages. The
# weights are obtained using the tree we have constructed.
wt_df <- data.frame(tip = supertree$tip.label, weight = BM(phy = supertree))
write.csv(wt_df, "data/weights.csv", row.names = FALSE)

```


Figure 1: Supertree of 496 languages used in this study.

Table 4: Raw and genealogically-sensitive proportions results. Results for specific satellite types indicate, among languages that have SSP violations in a margin, the proportion which have that specific satellite type.

Satellites	Margin	Raw proportions		Genealogically-sensitive	
		Merged	Split	Merged	Split
Any SSP violation	onset	26.6%	35.7%	32.1%	39.4%
Any SSP violation	coda	24.4%	29.2%	29.6%	37.4%
Any SSP violation	either	35.9%	45.2%	43.1%	51.7%
Any SSP violation	both	15.1%	19.8%	18.6%	25.1%
Sibilant	onset	72.0%	54.8%	76.9%	65.2%
Non-sibilant obstruent	onset	29.5%	22.6%	40.6%	33.8%
Nasal	onset	22.0%	49.7%	26.6%	44.6%
Approximant	onset	40.9%	30.5%	42.1%	34.3%
Sibilant	coda	36.4%	67.6%	44.4%	76.4%
Non-sibilant obstruent	coda	21.5%	20.0%	27.8%	24.0%
Nasal	coda	46.3%	38.6%	44.6%	35.3%
Approximant	coda	66.1%	55.2%	68.0%	53.9%

5 Raw and genealogically-sensitive results

Table 4 shows results as both raw and genealogically-sensitive proportions.

Table 5: Range of lengths of wordlists in the dataset

Wordlist length	Percentage of wordlists at this length or shorter
0%	49
5%	272
10%	299
15%	310
20%	320
25%	332
30%	350
35%	392
40%	427
45%	477
50%	584
55%	721
60%	799
65%	921
70%	971
75%	1030
80%	1090
85%	1183
90%	1442
95%	1961
100%	7659

6 Wordlist sizes

Wordlists were screened to remove duplicate phonological forms in the same language, since CLICS2 in some cases contains many duplicates. The resulting wordlist sizes range from 49 to 7659 with a mean of 835 and median of 584. Table 5 conveys the range of list sizes.

Table 6: Rate at which satellite types were missed in onsets

Sample size	Approximant	Nasal (merged)	Nasal (split)	Sibilant
260	4.4%	2.5%	4.8%	1.1%
294	4.2%	2.3%	4.5%	0.9%
304	4.1%	2.2%	4.4%	0.8%
316	4.1%	2.2%	4.4%	0.8%
328	3.9%	2.1%	4.2%	0.7%
350	3.9%	2.0%	4.0%	0.7%
392	3.6%	1.8%	3.8%	0.5%
427	3.4%	1.7%	3.5%	0.4%
477	3.2%	1.5%	3.3%	0.3%
584	2.6%	1.3%	2.7%	0.1%
721	2.1%	1.0%	2.1%	0.0%
799	1.7%	0.9%	1.8%	0.0%
921	1.3%	0.6%	1.4%	0.0%
971	1.1%	0.6%	1.3%	0.0%
1030	1.0%	0.5%	1.1%	0.0%

7 Monte Carlo sampling

We took the longest 20% of wordlists ($N = 100$) and then sampled from them, creating shorter, subset wordlists whose lengths now matched the lengths in Table 5, corresponding to $\{5\%, 10\%, \dots, 70\%, 75\%\}$ of the dataset (i.e., containing only $\{260, 296, \dots, 971, 1030\}$ words). For each of the 100 long wordlists and for each of the smaller sample sizes, we extracted 1000 random samples of that size and observed which sonority satellite types were absent in the sampled, shorter lists but present in the corresponding full list. In the 1000 samples, we observe the rate at which a satellite is missing (e.g., a rate of 2.5 indicates that in the 1000 samples, it was missing in 25 of them). Tables 6 and 7 show the average of such rates in the $N = 100$ long wordlists, for sibilant, approximant and nasal satellites.¹ Unless indicated, the results for split and merged methods are the same (because the methods do not affect the counts of the satellite type). These results supply an estimate of how many satellite types are likely to have been missed by chance, in general, by including the shorter wordlists in our dataset. The code used to perform this analysis is below.

¹Non-sibilant obstruent satellites do not occur in any of the 100 long wordlists, so their rates could not be estimated by this technique. Given the overall rarity of non-sibilant obstruent satellites, the expected rates are very low.

Table 7: Rate at which satellite types were missed in codas

Sample size	Approximant	Nasal	Sibilant (merged)	Sibilant (split)
260	6.7%	3.9%	5.1%	2.9%
294	6.3%	3.5%	4.8%	2.6%
304	6.2%	3.4%	4.6%	2.5%
316	6.0%	3.3%	4.6%	2.5%
328	5.9%	3.1%	4.5%	2.4%
350	5.7%	2.9%	4.3%	2.3%
392	5.3%	2.5%	3.9%	2.0%
427	5.0%	2.3%	3.7%	1.8%
477	4.6%	1.9%	3.4%	1.7%
584	3.9%	1.3%	2.6%	1.2%
721	3.2%	0.8%	1.8%	0.7%
799	2.9%	0.6%	1.4%	0.5%
921	2.5%	0.3%	0.7%	0.2%
971	2.3%	0.2%	0.6%	0.2%
1030	2.2%	0.1%	0.4%	0.1%

```

# Helper function
sum_satellites = function(df) {
  # (df should be grouped by doculect)
  df %>%
    summarise(
      n_mg_in_app = sum(mg_sat_initial == "approximant", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_in_nas = sum(mg_sat_initial == "nasal", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_in_sib = sum(mg_sat_initial == "sibilant", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_in_obs = sum(mg_sat_initial == "obstuent", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_fi_app = sum(mg_sat_final == "approximant", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_fi_nas = sum(mg_sat_final == "nasal", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_fi_sib = sum(mg_sat_final == "sibilant", na.rm = T),
      n_mg_fi_obs = sum(mg_sat_final == "obstuent", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_in_app = sum(sp_sat_initial == "approximant", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_in_nas = sum(sp_sat_initial == "nasal", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_in_sib = sum(sp_sat_initial == "sibilant", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_in_obs = sum(sp_sat_initial == "obstuent", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_fi_app = sum(sp_sat_final == "approximant", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_fi_nas = sum(sp_sat_final == "nasal", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_fi_sib = sum(sp_sat_final == "sibilant", na.rm = T),
      n_sp_fi_obs = sum(sp_sat_final == "obstuent", na.rm = T),
      .groups = "keep"
    ) %>%
    pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("n_"), names_to = "x", values_to = "n") %>%
    mutate(
      analysis = ifelse(str_detect(x, "mg"), "mg", "sp"),
      satellite = str_sub(x, -3, -1),
      position = ifelse(str_detect(x, "fi"), "final", "initial")
    ) %>%
    select(-x)
}

# Load and unpack the dataframe
lex_dat <- read_tsv(file = "data/MC_test_data.tsv")
row_reps <- rep(1:nrow(lex_dat), times = lex_dat$n)
lex_dat <- lex_dat[row_reps, ] %>% group_by(doculect)

# Sum satellites present in the full data
full_dat <-
  lex_dat %>% sum_satellites() %>% rename(n_full = n) %>%
  mutate(is_any_full = n_full > 0)

# MC sampling
n_samples = 1000
sample_sizes <- c(260, 294, 304, 316, 328, 350, 392, 427,
                 477, 584, 721, 799, 921, 971, 1030)
set.seed(2022)
mc_results <- NULL
for (size in sample_sizes) {
  # Get sampled lexicons
  new_results <-
    lapply(1:n_samples, function(i) {
      lex_dat %>%

```

```

    slice_sample(n = size) %>%
    sum_satellites() %>%
    left_join(full_dat, by = c("doculect", "analysis", "satellite", "position")) %>%
    mutate(is_any_sampled = n > 0, missing_any = is_any_full - is_any_sampled)
  }) %>% bind_rows()

# Keep just a summary
new_results <-
  new_results %>%
  group_by(analysis, position, satellite) %>%
  summarise(mean_missing_any = mean(missing_any), .groups = "keep")

mc_results <- bind_rows(mc_results, new_results %>% mutate(sample_size = size))
}

```

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